

The nature of dark energy and discussions on relevant phenomena

Abstract:

From the discrepancy between theoretical predictions and actual observations, we can find something beyond previous understanding exists. In following content, a gravitation effect deduced from the principle of equivalence will be introduced. It derives from the place with lower curvature and will cause redshift when light is transmitting in space among galaxies. Meanwhile, it can be considered as the repulsion from mass, and provide a reasonable explanation for the concept of inertia.

Logical arguments:

The logical starting point of my finding originates from a series of contradictions between theoretical predictions and actual observations.

Theoretical predictions:

- 1) According to the gravitational field equation, the mass causes the space-time curvature, which is presented as the sensory gravitational effect.
- 2) When curved to a certain extent (mass pressed into its Schwarzschild radius), it will make everything (including light) impossible to escape.
- 3) The light emitted from the gravitational field shows gravitational redshift. When the redshift reaches a certain degree, the light will be completely redshifted from the whole spectrum. When the light from the outside comes into the gravitational field, it will show gravitational blueshift.

Actual observations:

- 1) Redshift observed by supernova groups indicate that galaxies are accelerating away from us. If the acceleration is supposed to be caused by a gravitational field from far distance (or a repulsive field from our direction), obviously there isn't enough source of mass to support the gravitational field.
- 2) Galaxies beyond the Hubble radius cannot be observed. If the light is supposed to be extremely curved and trapped, it seems to be trapped outside the gravitational field.
- 3) When light travels from a distant place through astronomical scale of low mass density space, and comes into our gravitational field, it also seems redshifted, not blueshifted.

The above 1), 2) and 3) from predictions and observations are contradictory, respectively. Hence, previous researchers introduced the concept of dark energy, which leads to the repulsive force of the universe in large-scale space, and the accelerated expansion of the universe. This expansion consequently leads to the separation of the visual galaxies, and then causes the redshift phenomenon. The dark energy is always represented by a cosmological constant. However, there's a better solution to let the curvature to explain the phenomena, rather than a constant.

In order to solve the above problems, this finding is deduced through the following logical argumentation process:

1. As per the principle of equivalence, a space-time with lower mass density (relative negative curvature) than our (observer's) position also produces a sensory gravitational effect. The demonstration process is as follows (Fig. 1):

Fig. 1: Analogy of the gravitation produced by negative curvature

Assuming you are driving the black car with $5a$ rightward acceleration; the other white cars are moving with $2a$ rightward acceleration. In the view of white cars, you are actually with $5a$ rightward acceleration; however, seemingly with $3a$ rightward acceleration. Meanwhile, in the view of yourself, the white cars are actually with $2a$ rightward acceleration; however, seemingly with $3a$ leftward acceleration.

When doing the equivalent transformation: You are in the black car and keep stationary relative to a $5g$ leftward gravitation field; the other white cars are keeping stationary relative to a $2g$ leftward gravitation field. In the view of white cars, you are actually in the $5g$ leftward gravitation field; however, seemingly in the $3g$ leftward gravitation field. Meanwhile, in the view of yourself, the white cars are actually in the $2g$ leftward gravitation field; however, seemingly in the $3g$ rightward gravitation field. This $3g$ rightward gravitation field can be seemed as an attractive gravitation field from lower curvature place or a repulsive gravitation field from the direction of mass.

We can find the seemingly $3g$ rightward gravitation field is the source of the gravitation generated from the void parts of universe. This situation is really common in our daily world; however, the self-correcting function based on our daily experience can always help us to ignore the seemingly $3a$ leftward acceleration of the white cars.

This phenomenon can also be explained by the effect of tidal force. We can feel the $5g$ leftward gravitation field, and can observe the $3g$ rightward gravitation field. This will cause the space between them seem to be stretched, and cause a larger redshift than our expectation. This kind of stretching will be represented as a sensory repulsive effect.

This is also similar with a tidal effect caused by the sun or the moon to the earth. Tides are produced on both sides of the earth. This phenomenon is usually explained as: The rise of tides on the back side of the earth is due to the partial release of centrifugal inertia force against gravitation. However, when interpreted from the aspect of curvature, it is because the curvature of the front side and center of the earth is larger than that of the back side of the earth.

2. The gravitational field deduced from the above equivalent principle, which is

also the inner nature of dark energy, leads to the redshift. The demonstration process is as follows (Fig. 2):

Fig. 2: Cumulative effect of negative curvature over astronomical distances

The above image shows that when mass curves the space-time to positive curvature, from our point of view (on the earth), the positive curvature will bend the light to the direction of high mass density, and cause a gravitational redshift. If we interpret this from the aspect of energy, it is the gravitational field that transforms the energy of light into gravitational potential energy. When reaching a certain degree, the light will be redshifted out of the whole spectrum.

However, when we observe the lower curvature place (the region between galaxies in the universe), according to the above equivalent principle effect, the sensory gravitational field will point to the lower curvature place. If explained from the aspect of geometric, the small negative curvature will also cause the light to bended slightly (deviated away from the mass direction), which will lead to the continuous bending of the light in a large scale range when transmitting, and then make the light can't escape the trap of curvature. If explained from the aspect of energy, it is the attractive gravitation field from lower curvature place (or repulsive graviton field from the direction of mass), leads to energy conversion, when the light is transmitting from faraway place to our galaxies and causes the redshift.

The negative curvature acts as a concave lens, red-shifting the light with similar mechanism as observed in positive curvature. Even miniscule redshifts in a nearly flat space can become observable over astronomical distance accumulation. Obviously, we could add cosmological constant to the equation to make it consistent with the observation; however, it didn't solve the problem once and for all. Furthermore, it brings in dark energy as a new concept to be explained. My suggestion will be provided in following content.

3. Gravitation does not always point to the direction of mass density, but points to the location existing curvature difference with the observing location, and will also produce the repulsive force caused by mass. The demonstration process is as follows:

In Fig. 1, in order to explain the existence of dark energy, the white cars are uniformly

set to have a rightward acceleration of $2a$ (assuming the low-density space-time in the universe has the same curvature). However, when we consider the space-time curvature caused by a single particle with mass, we should assume that the four white cars have the rightward acceleration of $4a$, $3a$, $2a$ and $1a$ respectively, in the order from left side to right side. Then using the equivalent principle, in the views of the black car, four white cars from left side to right side will lean on the rightward gravitational field surface of $1g$, $2g$, $3g$, and $4g$ respectively.

Moreover, the farther away from the black car, the greater the rightward gravitational field, and resulting in a sensory repulsion effect. In fact, this is the intrinsic nature of the curvature of space-time. This repulsive effect exists between any two adjacent points in the curved space-time caused by a single particle with mass. This is not only applicable to large-scale space, but will have effect everywhere in its field. Through the differential geometry calculation, the similar analysis conclusion can be obtained. When the observed curvature is lower than where we (the observer) are, Lobachevskian geometry is a better choice to describe the situation.

This case shows that the curvature of space-time produced by a single particle with mass will produce two effects, and the actual effect is the superposition of the two:

1) When other particles (assuming that the curvature caused by other particles themselves can be ignored temporarily) move along the geodesic line in curved space-time, the attractive effect of spatial sense will be presented, and the trend of approaching to the central particle will be produced.

2) When other particles (ignoring the curvature caused by themselves) move along the geodesic line in the curved space-time, the distance between them gradually increases, and shows the repulsive effect of spatial sense.

This case also implies the acceleration and the conventional gravitation field not always have the equivalent effect. When observing a lower curvature place from a higher curvature place, these two will have opposite effect. More rigorously, the acceleration will have the equivalent effect with the gravitation field (caused by the curvature difference), but not equivalent with the conventional gravitation field (caused by the density of mass).

4. The above deduced repulsive effect can be used to better explain the concept of inertia. The demonstration process is as follows (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3: Analogy of the gravitation produced by negative curvature

As talked above, the attraction caused by low curvature place can also be seemed as a repulsion from mass. This effect will increase with distance increasing. Hence, any object with mass will be under the co-effect of all the mass in the whole universe around, which can interact with this object. One effect is the attraction, which will decrease while the distance is increasing. The other effect is the repulsion, which will increase while the distance is increasing. This object will be located at a balance position under the co-effect of these two effects.

The repulsion from all places will be quite stronger than the attraction considering the distance effect. However, the gravitation fields will simultaneously interact with every single atom or sub-atom entity in your body, so you will feel nothing about this kind of co-effect. Meanwhile, you are in a nearly balance position, so the co-effect of these repulsions will be balanced or neglected.

When you are acted upon by another kind of force, such as thrust caused by the electromagnetic force, the situation will be: First, You are in the balance position like in the bottom of the well. Then the thrust will try to push you to a higher place of the well. In that case, the co-effect will not be balanced, and the gravitation well will provide an opposite pushing effect to you. This opposite effect is caused by gravitation, and seemed to be caused by so called inertia.

5. Further discussion:

Base on the above arguments, the following conceptions can also be raised on further discussed:

1) Curvature is relative. When located in different curvature, the observers will get different conclusions for the same phenomenon?

2) In Einstein's elevator thought experiment, can the effect of horizontal tidal be neglected? If consider it in reality, will it cause a different conclusion? The phenomena observed in reality, such as gravitational lens effect of black hole, are only the result of observing high curvature from low curvature. If observed in the same curvature, will it be different?

3) The original equation of gravitational field is constructed by Riemannian geometry from the angle of 0 curvature observer, thus neglecting negative curvature. The cosmological constant introduced later can be regarded as the curvature difference (or absolute value) of the curvature of our position relative to the low-density space? However, this correction cannot solve the root cause, and will this constant be not applicable if we perform observation when locating in other curvature space-time. Therefore, is it more suitable to introduce Lobachevskian geometry or other methods to describe the curvature of the observer instead of the constant?

4) Is the repulsion effect mentioned above can make contribution to the establishment of a unified equation with electromagnetic field?

5) Can dark matter, Hubble radius, inertial reference system and many other related phenomena be explained by the same mechanism?

To better save your time, the above discussions are not unfolded here. If you are interested, you can also find the full text of the paper at the following address:

<https://zenodo.org/record/4022812#.X1pSTNnhQ-w>

The above is only a part of my paper. The other contents of the paper, due to the long length, and I think maybe only this part (starting from (6) dark matter and dark energy) will arouse readers' interest. Therefore, only this part is excerpted.

Summary:

Some contents above seem to conflict with the current objective facts. However, so-called objective facts are relative, and have their historical limitations. Just as people once believed that the earth is flat, the sun revolves around the earth, light travels in the ether, or parity is conserved. Any contradiction between theoretical predictions and actual observations will make people doubt the objective facts. And this is the time that the new theory emerges.

Although there is no specific verification test for this finding, many phenomena (such as dark energy) that can't be well explained by the existing theories can be used as the supporting basis.

I consider this finding is very important, and once proved will promote development of science in this field. Furthermore, it will broaden the human cognition of the universe and contribute to the development of human beings.

I admit, this finding is correct in logic, but lack in mathematical demonstration and quantitative coincidence verification with observation. Meanwhile, I also realize that it is impossible to make its complete theory (supplementing mathematical demonstration and observation quantitative coincidence verification) accepted by the world only by myself as an amateur. Every time I think about it, I can't sleep in peace all night.

Previously, the content of this finding has been sent out to several universities, asking for help. However, there is no direct feedback. Hence, this time if you consider this theory is reasonable and helpful, could it be convenient for you to help let it be further verified? (e.g. verifying it in the mathematical demonstration, or proceeding observation coincidence verification, or reminding universities, observatories and related research institutions to take heed of this finding and perform further verification)?

It's not for myself. For Science!

Many thanks for your patience to read this whole article.

Any concern or help from your side would be highly appreciated.

Waiting for your reply.